

On the Choice of Parameters for the Local Block Bootstrap in the Locally Stationary Setting

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Abstract

This paper addresses the choice of bootstrap parameters in the local block bootstrap for locally stationary processes. A simulation study shows the impact of these choices on coverage results for empirical characteristic functions (ECFs) of α -stable distributions. As theoretical foundation, a bootstrap central limit theorem is proposed to circumvent the dependence on the normal distribution while formulating bootstrap confidence intervals.

Key Words: local stationarity, local block bootstrap, α -stable distributions

1. Introduction

Dealing with time-varying linear processes, their stationary companion processes come in handy for proving various results. However, especially considering limit distributions, their lack of observability hampers statistical procedures like hypothesis testing. In this case, the so-called local block bootstrap established by Dowla et al. (2013) provides a sound way out. Said bootstrap procedure is based on the choice of different bootstrap parameters which each have a distinct impact on the simulation results. In this paper, the influence of different parameter choices is illustrated with an extended simulation study using α -stable distributions in combination with ECFs. The former is a wide class of distributions ensuring the transferability of the obtained results, whereas the latter opens the way to various procedures including independence testing. Additionally, a bootstrap central limit theorem allowing for the formulation of bootstrap confidence intervals by the pivotal method without relying on the normal distribution is presented.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides the mathematical background from the model assumptions to the bootstrap procedure. Moreover, it closes with the statement of the bootstrap central limit theorem. Subsequently, the simulation setup is presented in Section 3 together with a short overview of α -stable distributions and their characteristic functions (CFs). The section also contains the simulation results. The paper wraps up with a short conclusion and outlook in Section 4.

2. Mathematical Setting

We focus on linear locally stationary processes based on Dahlhaus (2012). Therefore, let $(X_{t,T})_{t=1}^T$, $T \in \mathbb{N}$, be a linear, time-varying process of form

$$X_{t,T} = \mu\left(\frac{t}{T}\right) + \sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} a_{t,T}(j) \varepsilon_{t-j}$$

with a mean function $\mu(\cdot)$, coefficients $(a_{t,T}(j))$ and innovations (ε_t) . Supposing the fulfillment of certain assumptions, there exists a strictly stationary process $(\bar{X}_t(u))$ which is the local approximation of the previously defined process in a neighborhood of a fixed time point $u = \frac{t}{T}$. More precisely, it holds

$$\bar{X}_t(u) = \mu(u) + \sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} a(u, j) \varepsilon_{t-j}.$$

Thus, the companion process possesses the same mean function and the same innovation process as the original process, only the coefficients $(a(u, j))$ have changed. The necessary regularity conditions ensuring the existence of the local approximation are the following:

Assumption 1.

- i. *The innovations are independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.), centered and have $(\frac{2+\delta}{2})$ -th absolute moments for some $\delta \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$.*
- ii. *The coefficients decay exponentially and are sufficiently smooth over time.*
- iii. *The coefficients $a_{t,T}(j)$ and $a(\frac{t}{T}, j)$ are adequately close.*
- iv. *The mean function is continuously differentiable.*

For a more detailed description, it is referred to Beering (2021).

The bootstrap procedure we are using is tailor-made for the locally stationary setting. In general, the basic bootstrap approach means drawing with replacement from a sample. However, it is not possible to represent the dependence structure of the original sample correctly that way. A solution to this was proposed by Dowla et al. (2013) in form of the LBB for trend estimation for locally stationary processes. By choosing blocks such that their indices are close to the ones of the corresponding blocks of the original process, the dependence structure is transferred to the bootstrap world. In detail, to replace a block of length L_T , the indices are shifted by a random number. The LBB algorithm reads as follows:

Algorithm 1 (Bootstrap algorithm).

- 1) Consider a blocklength L_T depending on T .
 - a) Select a window parameter $D_T \in (0, 1)$ such that $TD_T \in \mathbb{N}$.
 - b) Generate i.i.d. integers $k_0, \dots, k_{\lfloor T/L_T \rfloor - 1}$ via a discrete uniform distribution on $[-C_D TD_T, C_D TD_T]$, where C_D is a positive, finite constant.
 - c) Define $X_{1,T}^*, \dots, X_{T,T}^*$ as

$$X_{j+iL_T,T}^* := X_{j+iL_T+k_i,T}$$

for $j = 1, \dots, L_T$, $i = 0, \dots, \lfloor \frac{T}{L_T} \rfloor - 1$.

- d) Construct the bootstrap estimator by replacing $X_{t,T}$ with $X_{t,T}^*$
- 2) If a chosen index i of a block lays outside of $[1, T]$, use $-k_i$ in place of k_i for the whole block.

In lieu of the discrete uniform distribution generating $k_0, \dots, k_{\lfloor T/L_T \rfloor - 1}$, other choices are allowed. However, the discrete uniform distribution falls in line with the original block bootstrap algorithm for stationary processes. Note that the second part of Algorithm 1 preserves the interrelated dependence structure on the one hand while simultaneously making sure no observation appears twice in the same block.

Although we make use of the original algorithm of Dowla et al. (2013), we need to adjust the requirements imposed on the bootstrap parameters, which will later be the main part of our investigations:

Assumption 2.

For blocklength L_T and window parameter D_T , it holds

- i. $L_T = o\left((b_T T)^{\frac{\delta}{2(1+\delta)}}\right)$ and
 - ii. $(b_T T)^{\frac{2\delta}{2+\delta}} \leq C_D T D_T \leq (b_T T)^{\frac{1}{2+\delta}}$,
- respectively, where $C_D < \infty$ is a positive constant.

The framework of our simulation study is borrowed by Jentsch et al. (2020) as we take up on ECFs. These come in handy in many applications from monitoring interrelations between two time series using distance correlation as introduced by Székely et al. (2007) to independence testing, see e.g. Beerling (2021). Moreover, ECFs can be used when the application of moment-based methods is not possible. The CF of the companion process $(\tilde{X}_t(u))$ reads as follows:

$$\varphi_X(u; s) := E e^{is\tilde{X}_0(u)}, s \in \mathbb{R}.$$

However, as the companion process is not observable, we need to fall back on observations $X_{1,T}, \dots, X_{T,T}$ from the original process to construct the empirical version of $\varphi_X(u; s)$. Moreover, instead of using the classical moment estimator, we need to account for the locality. This leads to the use of a kernel function K and a bandwidth b_T depending on T , and we obtain the CF's local observation analogue, that is

$$\widehat{\varphi}_X(u; s) := \frac{1}{b_T T} \sum_{t=1}^T K\left(\frac{t}{T} - u\right) e^{isX_{t,T}}, s \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Both kernel and bandwidth need to satisfy the usual requirements, which are summed up in the following assumption:

Assumption 3.

- i. The function $K: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is symmetric and Lipschitz continuous with Lipschitz constant $C_{Lip,K}$. Besides, it integrates up to 1 and has compact support $[-1, 1]$.
- ii. The bandwidth sequence (b_T) is non-negative and fulfills $b_T^2 T \rightarrow \infty$ and $b_T^3 T \rightarrow 0$ as T tends to ∞ .

With our simulation study, we aim to investigate the impact the bootstrap parameters have on the coverage for both the real and imaginary part of $(b_T T)^{1/2}(\widehat{\varphi}_X(u; s) - \varphi_X(u; s))$ as well as for the absolute value of said expression. Therefore, we need the following result:

Theorem 1.

Under Assumptions 1 to 3, both

$$\sup_{v \in \mathbb{R}} P^* \left((b_T T)^{1/2} R \left(\widehat{\varphi}_X^*(u; s) - E^* \widehat{\varphi}_X^*(u; s) \right) \leq v \right) - P \left((b_T T)^{1/2} R \left(\widehat{\varphi}_X(u; s) - \varphi_X(u; s) \right) \leq v \right)$$

and

$$\sup_{v \in \mathbb{R}} \left| P^* \left((b_T T)^{1/2} I \left(\widehat{\varphi}_X^*(u; s) - E^* \widehat{\varphi}_X^*(u; s) \right) \leq v \right) - P \left((b_T T)^{1/2} I \left(\widehat{\varphi}_X(u; s) - \varphi_X(u; s) \right) \leq v \right) \right|$$

tend to 0 in P -probability as T tends to ∞ for all $u \in [0, 1]$ and every $s \in \mathbb{R}$.

Theorem 1 opens the way to formulate bootstrap confidence intervals for both $R\varphi_X(u; s)$ and $I\varphi_X(u; s)$ by the pivotal method circumventing the normal distribution.

3. Numerical Results

In order to illustrate the impact of the bootstrap parameters, we conduct a simulation study using α -stable distributions. This class of distributions is determined by a location parameter $\mu \in \mathbb{R}$, a characteristic exponent $\alpha \in (0, 2]$, a skewness parameter $\beta \in [-1, 1]$ and a scale parameter $\gamma \geq 0$, allowing both light- and heavy-tailed distributions to be included. The corresponding CF reads as follows:

$$\varphi_{\mu, \alpha, \beta, \gamma}(s) = \exp\left(i\mu s - \gamma|s|^\alpha(1 + i\beta \operatorname{sgn}(s) \tau(s, \alpha))\right)$$

for $s \in \mathbb{R}$ with

$$\tau(s, \alpha) = \begin{cases} \tan\left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{2}\right), & \alpha \neq 1, \\ \frac{2}{\pi} \log|s|, & \alpha = 1. \end{cases}$$

Besides its versatility, this class has a special advantage regarding linear processes: Given the innovations (ε_t) follow an α -stable distribution with parameters $(\mu, \alpha, \beta, \gamma)$, linear processes $(\widetilde{X}_t(u))$ also follow an α -stable distribution with parameters

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\alpha}(u) &= \alpha, \\ \tilde{\beta}(u) &= \beta \frac{\sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} \operatorname{sgn}(a(u, j)) |a(u, j)|^\alpha}{\sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} |a(u, j)|^\alpha}, \\ \tilde{\mu}(u) &= \mu, \\ \tilde{\gamma}(u) &= \gamma \sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} |A(u, j)|^\alpha. \end{aligned}$$

In consequence, the companion process has the time-varying CF

$$\varphi(u; s) = \varphi_{\tilde{\mu}(u), \tilde{\alpha}(u), \tilde{\beta}(u), \tilde{\gamma}(u)}(s) = \exp\left(i\tilde{\mu}(u)s - \tilde{\gamma}(u)|s|^{\tilde{\alpha}(u)}\left(1 + i\tilde{\beta}(u) \operatorname{sgn}(s) \tilde{\tau}(s, \tilde{\alpha}(u))\right)\right)$$

for any $s \in \mathbb{R}$ with

$$\tilde{\tau}(s, \tilde{\alpha}(u)) = \begin{cases} \tan\left(\frac{\pi\tilde{\alpha}(u)}{2}\right), & \tilde{\alpha}(u) \neq 1, \\ \frac{2}{\pi} \log|s|, & \tilde{\alpha}(u) = 1. \end{cases}$$

Returning to ECFs, they work especially well with α -stable distributions due to the non-availability of certain moments. Broadly speaking, a process having an α -stable distribution for $\alpha < 2$ possess every number of finite absolute moments less than α . Therefore, second absolute finite moments are rare and even first ones do not always exist, making the use of moment-based methods difficult.

This simulation study, in particular, uses a locally stationary process $(X_{t,T})$ with

$$X_{t,T} = \begin{cases} 0.7 \sin\left(2\pi \frac{1}{T}\right) \varepsilon_0 + \varepsilon_1, & t = 1, \\ 0.7 \sin\left(2\pi \frac{t}{T}\right) X_{t-1,T} + \varepsilon_t, & t = 2, \dots, T. \end{cases}$$

Hence, $(X_{t,T})$ is a time-varying centered AR(1) process. Following Dahlhaus (2012), the appurtenant companion process is built as

$$\tilde{X}_t(u) = \sum_{j \in \mathbb{N}_0} (0.7 \sin(2\pi u))^j \varepsilon_{t-j}.$$

The innovations (ε_t) form an i.i.d. sequence with an α -stable marginal distribution with parameters

$$\mu = 0, \alpha = 1.5, \beta = 0, \gamma = 0.5.$$

Firstly, we vary the blocklength. This is done by working with $L_T = C_L \tilde{L}_T$, where $\tilde{L}_T = \lfloor (2\lfloor b_T T \rfloor + 1)^{0.1} \rfloor$ and C_L is a varying prefactor. Subsequently, we focus on the window size. All simulations are carried out for sample sizes from $T = 3000$ to $T = 15000$ with a target value of 0.95 for the coverage. Based on Theorem 1, we consider the empirical 0.025- and 0.975-bootstrap quantile to obtain said significance level. For each sample size T , we obtain three different coverages per bootstrap parameter, displayed in Tables 1 to 4. The first belongs to the real part of $(b_T T)^{1/2}(\widehat{\varphi}_X(u; s) - \varphi_X(u; s))$, the second to the imaginary one and the third to the appurtenant absolute value.

Table 1: Coverage results for varying blocklengths

T	$5\tilde{L}_T$	$10\tilde{L}_T$	$20\tilde{L}_T$
3000	0.895	0.910	0.875
	0.955	0.950	0.915
	0.930	0.920	0.905
5000	0.890	0.940	0.920
	0.980	0.945	0.940
	0.915	0.945	0.955
10000	0.945	0.925	0.905
	0.935	0.930	0.930
	0.955	0.950	0.920
15000	0.935	0.930	0.935
	0.960	0.970	0.920
	0.960	0.950	0.935

Table 1 shows the coverage results for different blocklengths. Overall, the results are pretty close to the target value of 0.95. However, there are certain differences. In most cases, the highest coverage rate is achieved for the imaginary part or the absolute value. Besides, the results become better for larger sample sizes, which falls perfectly in line with Theorem 1. Comparing the columns, it turns out that the best results are obtained for $C_L = 10$.

Table 2: Coverage results for varying window sizes for $\tau = 0.3$

T	TD_T	$5TD_T$	$10TD_T$	$20TD_T$
3000	0.745	0.905	0.925	0.900
	0.845	0.935	0.915	0.960
	0.775	0.930	0.910	0.930
5000	0.780	0.920	0.905	0.900
	0.825	0.970	0.940	0.955
	0.790	0.950	0.905	0.935
10000	0.605	0.855	0.950	0.960
	0.690	0.930	0.960	0.945
	0.580	0.875	0.960	0.955
15000	0.685	0.900	0.870	0.925
	0.720	0.920	0.925	0.945
	0.635	0.920	0.915	0.945

Now we move on to the window size. According to Assumption 2, we are able to calculate TD_T via $TD_T = [(2\lfloor b_T T \rfloor + 1)^\tau]$ for a suitable exponent τ . In our case, we choose τ equal to 0.3, 0.35 and 0.4. Moreover, we chose different prefactors C_D from 1 to 20.

Table 3: Coverage results for varying window sizes for $\tau = 0.35$

T	TD_T	$5TD_T$	$10TD_T$	$20TD_T$
3000	0.855	0.930	0.910	0.950
	0.930	0.915	0.950	0.950
	0.865	0.920	0.920	0.935
5000	0.850	0.945	0.940	0.905
	0.895	0.935	0.945	0.935
	0.870	0.945	0.945	0.935
10000	0.695	0.910	0.925	0.935
	0.735	0.925	0.930	0.935
	0.670	0.910	0.950	0.920
15000	0.760	0.900	0.930	0.925
	0.795	0.855	0.970	0.920
	0.775	0.910	0.950	0.920

The results for the variation of window size are displayed in Tables 2 to 4. Again, we notice that the coverage rates are, in most cases, close to the target value. Once more, the values for the imaginary part and the absolute value are nearer to 0.95 as the ones for the real part of the difference in question. Nevertheless, the coverage rates get closer to the target value, as before, for growing T . However, comparing all three tables in question, we see the best results for $\tau = 0.35$. This is no surprise, as we have both a lower and an upper bound for $C_D TD_T$ stated in Assumption 2. This value for τ ensures equal distance to both bounds. Shifting our focus to the prefactor C_D , we observe that the larger the sample size, the larger the prefactor should be to obtain the best coverage results.

Table 4: Coverage results for varying window sizes for $\tau = 0.4$

T	TD_T	$5TD_T$	$10TD_T$	$20TD_T$
3000	0.885	0.925	0.900	0.940
	0.915	0.915	0.960	0.965
	0.900	0.910	0.930	0.970
5000	0.870	0.905	0.900	0.940
	0.915	0.940	0.955	0.920
	0.905	0.905	0.935	0.940
10000	0.835	0.955	0.935	0.920
	0.835	0.935	0.940	0.905
	0.870	0.950	0.920	0.945
15000	0.835	0.870	0.925	0.970
	0.865	0.925	0.945	0.955
	0.840	0.915	0.945	0.965

4. Concluding Remarks

In our simulation study, we have seen that varying the bootstrap parameters has an influence on the coverage results as expected. However, there are more possibilities to tweak said parameters, leading to many potential choices of bootstrap parameters. Nevertheless, even a comparably bad choice still leads to satisfying results. Moreover, it became clear that the sample size has a bigger impact on the results than the choice of bootstrap parameters. Therefore, it would be worth exploring the consequences of different bandwidths since the bandwidth controls the effective sample size used in the estimators via the kernel function. In addition to that, the bandwidth has also an influence on the bootstrap parameters, as it controls the bounds in Assumption 2. This aspect is part of future work.

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